

Executive Summary on the 2024 UAP Workshop:

“Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP): A Dialogue on Science, Public Engagement and Communication”

May 15-17, 2024

Associated Universities, Inc. (AUI)
Suite 700, 2650 Park Tower Drive, Vienna, VA 22180

Workshop sponsored by:

National Science Foundation, via ASTRO ACCEL
NSF Award #2301922

Workshop Planning Committee:

Amanda Barrera (AUI)
Yasmin Catricheo (AUI)
Anica Miller-Rushing (AUI)
Saeed Salimpour (International Astronomical Union)
Tim Spuck (NSF/AUI)
Gretchen Stahlman (Florida State University)

ASTRO ACCEL Core Organizing Group (COG):

Amanda Barrera, Kelly Blumenthal, Nic Bonne, Yasmin Catricheo, Bret Feranchak, Anica Miller-Rushing, Saeed Salimpour, Gretchen Stahlman, Tim Spuck, Tiffany Stone Wolbrecht

Workshop participants (who explicitly agreed to be named):

Jasodhara Bhattacharya	Independence Science
Laura Domine	Harvard University, Center for Astrophysics
Salman Hameed	Hampshire College / Kainaat Studios
Leslie Kean	Independent
Jill Malusky	National Radio Astronomy Observatory & Green Bank Observatory
Michael McConville	International Planetarium Society
Dean Miskovich	Oil Region Astronomical Society
Steven Mitchell	Green Bank Pictures & AUI
Demitri Muna	Nightlight Research
Vishnu Reddy	University of Arizona
Bri Rodriguez	Florida State University
Christian Stepien	National UFO Reporting Center
Dan Tell	California Academy of Sciences
Beatriz Villarroel	Nordita, Stockholm University, Sweden
Diana Walsh Pasulka	University of North Carolina Wilmington
Iya Whiteley	Center for Space Medicine, UCL

Disclaimer: Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material or the UAP Workshop are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.

Introduction and Purpose

The scientific community and governments worldwide have recently taken renewed interest in legitimizing the study of Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP), which leads to important implications for various fields of study, as well as society as a whole. Also known as UFO's, UAP research was historically labeled “fringe science”, but is gaining credibility through the potential implications of UAP studies for further understanding our earth and space environments and addressing national security concerns (Pasulka, 2019; Yingling, Yingling & Bell, 2023). Recent developments emphasizing a need for rigorous scientific exploration of UAP include the declassification of government reports and videos documenting UAP encounters (Cooper, Blumenthal, & Kean, 2017; Kean & Blumenthal, 2017), and the establishment of new agencies and task forces to investigate UAP (ODNI, 2021; NASA, 2023; AARO, 2024). In parallel, academic and research institutions are dedicating resources to exploring how advanced technologies and methodologies can be deployed to gather and analyze data about UAP (Loeb & Laukien, 2022; Watters, et al., 2023). The scientific community is also recognizing UAP research as an interdisciplinary field that encompasses social and cultural studies, history, and policy, among others (Stahlman, 2024). This increasing mobilization across sciences and sectors presents new science communication and education challenges and opportunities for innovation in these areas as well.

To address these developments, a workshop titled “Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP): A Dialogue on Science, Public Engagement and Communication” was held May 15-17, 2024, in the Washington, D.C. area. The workshop was funded by the National Science Foundation (NSF) as a supplement award to the *Global Network for Accelerating Synergies Through Research On Astronomy Culture, Communication, Education and Learning* (ASTRO ACCEL) project. The event united a diverse group of participants, including academics, researchers, communication and education professionals and scholars, and aviation specialists. The workshop's main objectives were to foster interdisciplinary discussions and collaborations on UAP, develop strategies for effective communication and education, examine the societal impacts of UAP research, and incorporate UAP discussions into the broader context of the NSF ASTRO ACCEL initiative. The outcomes of the workshop will include a comprehensive report co-authored by participants with recommendations for future research and broader applications of the findings.

The ASTRO ACCEL project focuses on fostering interdisciplinary research and education in astronomy and related fields. By promoting collaboration and innovation, ASTRO ACCEL aims to advance scientific understanding and public engagement in astronomy and space sciences. UAP research intersects with numerous aspects of astronomy, from the analysis of atmospheric phenomena to the exploration of potential extraterrestrial life. UAP research also provides a unique opportunity to engage the public in scientific discourse and education. As public interest in UAP continues to grow, leveraging this curiosity can enhance engagement in astronomy and space sciences. Overall, integrating UAP studies within the broader ASTRO ACCEL network aligns well with the project's goals of advancing knowledge and facilitating collaboration, along with its broader mission of promoting science and cultural literacy.

Workshop Process and Structure

In June 2023, the NSF awarded a \$25,000 supplement to the original ASTRO ACCEL grant (#2301922) to host the UAP Workshop. A planning committee composed of ASTRO ACCEL leadership team members was formed (see acknowledgements on cover page), and May 2024 was identified as the preferred time frame for hosting the workshop at the AUI headquarters in Vienna, VA. The planning committee met on an as-needed basis to engage in workshop preparations, reporting back regularly to ASTRO ACCEL leadership and stakeholders.

Recruitment and Planning

ASTRO ACCEL planning committee members issued targeted invitations to qualified individuals based on desired expertise (see [Introduction](#)). Potential participants were invited to submit an Expression of Interest to attend the workshop (see [Appendix B](#) for the Expression of Interest invitation). Snowball sampling was utilized, as invitees were encouraged to forward the invitation or suggest alternate invitees. Expressions of Interest were reviewed by the committee and accepted between March – May 2024. Decisions were made to issue formal invitations based on participants' qualifications and travel support needs (considering limited budget for participant support).

Prior to the workshop, guidelines for conduct were communicated by email to all confirmed participants (see [Appendix C: Guidelines for Conduct](#)). Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval for the workshop was provided by Florida State University (see [Appendix D: Participant Consent Information Sheet](#)).

Twenty-five participants were selected and agreed to attend. Three additional guest presenters engaged in limited participation virtually. Six ASTRO ACCEL organizers participated and facilitated, and an NSF program officer attended as an observer but did not formally participate. Prior to the workshop, participants received suggested pre-reads to become familiar with the UAP topic and recent developments (see AARO, 2024; Condon & Gillmor, 1969; Cooper, Blumenthal & Kean, 2017; Gallaudet, 2024; Gieryn, 1983; Kean & Blumenthal, 2023; NASA, 2023; ODNI, 2021; Sol Foundation, 2024; Villarroel, 2024).

Workshop participants' primary areas of expertise are: Astronomy (x7); Government (x4); Education (x3); Visualization (x3); Anthropology (x1); Aviation (x1); Data Management (x1); Journalism (x1); Library & Information Science (x1); Media Production (x1); Oceanography (x1); Psychology (x1); Public Information (x1); Religious Studies (x1); and Sociology (x1).

Workshop Structure

Participant privacy was an important consideration throughout workshop planning. The committee wished to establish a neutral environment in which participants holding diverse beliefs and backgrounds would feel comfortable engaging. The planning committee decided not to publicize the workshop online beforehand to limit outside attention and encourage comfort and open discourse among an intimate group of participants. The guidelines for

conduct ([Appendix C](#)) further urged participants to avoid taking photos or attributing statements to individuals without permission.

The workshop itself was introduced on Day 1 through introductory presentations by facilitators Spuck and Stahlman. Spuck discussed the ASTRO ACCEL project and expectations for the workshop. To set the stage for the breakout sessions and guide discussions, Stahlman introduced two rhetorical frameworks ([Appendix E: Figures](#)).

First, the “Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (DIKW) Pyramid” metaphor ([Figure 1](#)) depicts data as the foundational element in a hierarchical pyramid. Data can be meaningless, while the next level - information - is structured data that can be interpreted. Knowledge surpasses information and is personal, subjective, local and culturally constructed, while the transformation to wisdom at the top of the pyramid is the desired synthesis of all data, information and knowledge.

Second, the “Phases of Information” metaphor ([Figure 2](#)) adapts the phases of matter framework in thermodynamics to depict an ecosystem in which information and communication transform across contexts ranging from curation to active research to broadcasted and dispersed information (prone to misinterpretation).

Three breakout sessions were introduced, designed primarily in alignment with the DIKW framework:

- Breakout #1: Phases of information
 - “The Data & The Information”
- Breakout #2: Educating about UAP
 - “The Communication”
- Breakout #3: Integrating UAP knowledge networks
 - “The Knowledge & The Wisdom”

The first breakout session targeted the data and information aspects of UAP studies, the second addressed the education and communication aspects (considered to be the “connective tissue” for the pyramid as data transitions into knowledge), and the third breakout session focused on building community as an environment conducive to knowledge and wisdom.

Throughout the workshop, the organizing team collected anonymous data in the form of notes stored in a shared Google Drive directory. For each breakout session, ASTRO ACCEL moderators also served as scribes (Anica Miller-Rushing, Tim Spuck, Gretchen Stahlman, Tiffany Stone-Wolbrecht).

Agenda

Per the agenda provided in [Appendix A: UAP Workshop Agenda](#), Breakout #1 was held in the morning of Day 1, Breakout #2 was held in the afternoon of Day 1, and Breakout #3 was held in two parts in the morning of Day 2.

Guest presentations by virtual participants were integrated into the workshop. A one-hour panel presentation delivered by Simon Steel and Bill Diamond about the Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence (SETI) on Day 1 informed the group about SETI activities and possibilities for engagement with UAP research. A 30-minute guest lecture by Beatriz Villarroel discussed her work to detect anomalous observations using astronomical plates.

Participants were also invited to give short “rapid-fire” presentations about their work in relation to UAP. Eleven participants elected to present in two one-hour time slots.

Networking opportunities were provided through meals and coffee breaks each day, including two hosted dinners on May 15 and May 16.

Breakout Session Descriptions

Breakout #1: Drawing upon the Phases of Information framework, participants were placed into “homogeneous” groups based on their expertise (see [Figure 3](#)). Breakout groups were asked to discuss 1) the types of information and data in each area that can support UAP Studies and communication about UAP (scholarly and general public); 2) tension points; and 3) how to facilitate appropriate “phase shifts” to avoid misinterpretation and construct useful evidence and knowledge. After a period of time, participants switched to “heterogeneous” groups to continue the discussion.

Breakout #2: Participants grouped themselves based on three areas of interest related to education - formal education (i.e. K-12), informal education (i.e. science communication with the public), and university-level education (i.e. undergraduate and graduate levels). Each group discussed how to respond to different scenarios presenting education and communication challenges. Scenarios are listed in [Appendix F](#).

Breakout #3: In Part I, participants self-selected into three topic areas: government and policy, academia, and communication & public engagement. Groups were asked to discuss 1) barriers to preventing cross collaboration across networks; 2) needs to help break down barriers; and 3) affordances to help build connections. Groups were also asked to identify 3-4 projects that would be beneficial to move these efforts forward. During a break, workshop organizers reviewed notes and identified four working groups suggested by participants. Part II of the breakout session focused on planning for these working groups (discussed in [Outcomes and Recommendations](#) section below).

Final Whole Group Discussion: The final hour of the workshop was spent synthesizing outcomes and suggesting content and structure for the final workshop report. To structure the discussion, participants were reminded of the initial workshop goals to focus on 1) developing effective communication and education strategies regarding UAP; 2) exploring the intersection of UAP research with societal implications; 3) understanding the data, information and knowledge ecosystems surrounding UAP studies; and 4) integrating discussions on UAP within the broader framework of the NSF ASTRO ACCEL project.

Outcomes and Recommendations

Working Groups

Four projects were selected for working group discussions in Breakout Session #3, with a goal of formally convening these working groups beyond the scope of the workshop:

- **Curricular Resources:** This working group addresses the lack of guidelines for teaching about UAP at all levels. The working group identified a need to share and discuss curricular materials and strategies across disciplines.
- **Web Portal:** This working group discussed a need for a web portal or online clearinghouse as a “one-stop-shop” for UAP content that can support science literacy.
- **Citizen Science Application:** An application was envisioned to collect UAP reports and help users identify objects observed. As an alternative to similar existing apps (such as Enigma Labs), this application would be citizen science oriented, not for profit, and open source.
- **Follow-on Event:** A strong outcome of the workshop is a need for a follow-on event, ideally within six months. This working group began discussing how to fund and implement another workshop and cultivate a community of practice.

General Recommendations/Themes

High-level recommendations and themes that emerged in relation to the aims of the workshop include:

- **Understanding the historical context:** It is necessary to review historical representations and timelines of UAP observations to inform current discussions. This includes identifying key stakeholders in the historical perspective, including academic and governmental contributions, and recognizing the long history of UAP observations.
- **Addressing stigma & building trust:** Stigma and negativity associated with studying UAPs must be addressed by working towards open and stigma-free communication regarding research. Trust can be built across networks by promoting structured data sharing, collaboration for development of instruments and methods, and respectful dialogue across contexts.
- **Exploring social & political frameworks:** It is important to investigate what individuals believe about UAPs and why through a social science lens. This includes examining the political, infrastructure, and information frameworks surrounding UAP research.
- **Next steps & action plans:** A key outcome of the workshop is to identify working groups and outline proposed action plans. We aim to establish clear goals and strategies to move forward with UAP research and communication.

Participant Feedback Survey

An anonymous survey was sent to participants following the workshop to obtain feedback, and 20 responses were received. To the question “Overall, how satisfied were you with the workshop?” 17 respondents were “Very Satisfied” and 3 respondents were “Somewhat Satisfied”. Positive feedback surrounded the range of participant backgrounds, respectful and open atmosphere, facilitation, and innovative approach to a complex topic. In terms of critical feedback, respondents suggested reducing the number of agenda items, providing more time for networking and presentations, mitigating technical glitches, and structuring sessions around the diverse participant representation.

Objectives Moving Forward

Plans for immediate next steps include:

- Working groups established in Breakout Session #3 will be convened to maintain momentum and make progress towards supporting community needs;
- Participants who indicated that they wish to co-author the final workshop report (white paper) will work to prepare the report;
- A follow-on workshop will be planned, including exploring sources and models for funding and support;
- The UAP Workshop will be integrated into ASTRO ACCEL activities, particularly the upcoming Summit that will be held adjacent to the International Astronomical Union (IAU) General Assembly in Cape Town, South Africa (August 3-5, 2024).

References

All-Domain Anomaly Resolution Office (2024). *Report on the Historical Record of U.S. Government Involvement with Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP), Volume I*.

Condon, E. U., & Gillmor, D. S. (1969). *Scientific study of unidentified flying objects*.

Cooper, H., Blumenthal, R., & Kean, L. (2017). *Glowing Auras and 'Black Money': The Pentagon's Mysterious U.F.O. Program—The New York Times*. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from <https://www.nytimes.com/2017/12/16/us/politics/pentagon-program-ufo-harry-reid.html>

Gallaudet, T. (2024). *Beneath the Surface: We May Learn More about UAP by Looking in the Ocean – The Sol Foundation*. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from <https://thesolfoundation.org/publication/beneath-the-surface-we-may-learn-more-about-uap-by-looking-in-the-ocean/>

Gieryn, T. F. (1983). Boundary-work and the demarcation of science from non-science: Strains and interests in professional ideologies of scientists. *American sociological review*, 781-795.

Kean, L. & Blumenthal, R. (2023, June 5). *Intelligence Officials Say U.S. Has Retrieved Craft of Non-Human Origin*. The Debrief. <https://thedebrief.org/intelligence-officials-say-u-s-has-retrieved-non-human-craft/>

Loeb, A., & Laukien, F. H. (2022). Overview of The Galileo Project. *Journal of Astronomical Instrumentation*. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S2251171723400032>

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (2023). *Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena Independent Study Team Report*. Retrieved from: <https://science.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/uap-independent-study-team-final-report.pdf>

Office of the Director of National Intelligence. (2021). *Preliminary assessment: Unidentified aerial phenomena*.

Pasulka, D. W. (2019). *American cosmic: UFOs, religion, technology*. Oxford University Press.

Sol Foundation (2024). *UAP in Crowded Skies: Atmospheric and Orbital Threat Reduction in an Age of Geopolitical Uncertainty – The Sol Foundation*. Retrieved May 30, 2024, from <https://thesolfoundation.org/publication/uap-in-crowded-skies-atmospheric-and-orbital-threat-reduction-in-an-age-of-geopolitical-uncertainty/>

Stahlman, G. R. (2024). Closing the Information Gap in Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP) Studies. In *International Conference on Information* (pp. 310-320). Springer, Cham.

Villarroel, B. (2024, January 21). *The Vanishing Star Enigma and the 1952 Washington D.C. UFO Wave*. The Debrief. <https://thedebrief.org/the-vanishing-star-enigma-and-the-1952-washington-d-c-ufo-wave/>

Watters, W. A., Loeb, A., Laukien, F., Cloete, R., Delacroix, A., Dobroshinsky, S., ... & Zorzano, M. P. (2023). The Scientific Investigation of Unidentified Aerial Phenomena (UAP) Using Multimodal Ground-Based Observatories. *Journal of Astronomical Instrumentation*, 12(01), 2340006.

Yingling, M. E., Yingling, C. W., & Bell, B. A. (2023). Faculty perceptions of unidentified aerial phenomena. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 1-15.

Appendix A: UAP Workshop Agenda

May 15 – 7 pm to 9 pm

- 7:00-9:00 pm: Networking Dinner @ Inca Social

May 16 – 9 am to 5 pm

- 8:00-9:00: Breakfast (in the meeting room - AUI building 7th floor)
- 9:00-9:15: Welcome, announcements, and workshop format overview (Tim Spuck, AUI)
- 9:15-9:30: Self-introduction of participants
- 9:30-9:45: Setting the stage: ASTRO ACCEL (Tim Spuck, AUI)
- 9:45-10:15: Setting the stage: UAP and Information (Gretchen Stahlman, FSU)
- 10:15-10:30: Coffee break
- 10:30-12:00: Breakout session #1: Phases of information
- 12:00-1:00: SETI panel and Q&A (Simon Steel & Bill Diamond, SETI)
- 1:00-2:00: Lunch (in the meeting room - AUI building 7th floor)
- 2:00-3:00: Participant presentations
- 3:00-3:15: Coffee break
- 3:15-4:45: Breakout session #2: Educating about UAP
- 4:45-5:00: Group discussion and setting Day 2 priorities
- 5:00: Day 1 concludes
- 6:00: Happy hour and dinner. Halstead at the Metro, 2655 Prosperity Ave., Fairfax, VA

May 17 - 9 am to 3 pm

- 8:00-9:00: Breakfast (in the meeting room - AUI building 7th floor))
- 9:00-9:15: Welcome and announcements
- 9:15-9:45: Guest speaker and Q&A (Beatriz Villarroel)
- 9:45-10:45: Breakout #3 (Part I): Integrating UAP knowledge networks
- 10:45-11:00: Coffee break
- 11:00-12:00: Breakout #3 (Part II): Working group action planning
- 12:00-1:00: Lunch (in the meeting room - AUI building 7th floor)
- 1:00-2:00: Participant presentations
- 2:00-3:00: Whole group discussion and outlining white paper
- 3:00: Workshop concludes

Appendix B: Invitation to Submit Expression of Interest

Subject: Invitation to submit Expression of Interest for NSF-funded Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP) Workshop

Dear [Recipient/Group Name],

Recent efforts to legitimize the study of Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP) within the scientific community have gained momentum. This brings significant implications for the advancement of knowledge in various disciplines, as well as national defense, and the public's perception of the nature and processes of science. I am writing to inform you of an **upcoming opportunity to participate in a workshop focused on exploring approaches for effective communication and education about UAP across the sciences and with the broader general public.** This workshop is funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) and hosted by the *Global Network for Accelerating Synergies Through Research On Astronomy Culture, Communication, Education and Learning* (ASTRO ACCEL).

The workshop, “Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP): A Dialogue on Science, Public Engagement and Communication,” will be held **May 16-17, 2024 in the Washington, D.C. area.** We will bring together a diverse group of experts including scholars, researchers, communication experts, educators, and traditional knowledge holders, to better understand the scientific frontiers of UAP (otherwise known as “UFO”) research and explore effective communication and education strategies for fostering discussions about UAP. By bridging the gap between scientific research and public understanding, the workshop aims to support scientific investigation of UAP by promoting science and cultural literacy and facilitating effective dialogue.

Our primary goal for the workshop is to stimulate interdisciplinary discourse and collaboration to address the complexities surrounding the topic of UAP. By convening experts and stakeholders from relevant backgrounds, we plan to generate a report outlining key interests and pathways for future research and work, including extending our findings to other controversial and high-profile topics in science. Focus areas for discussion include:

- Developing effective communication and education strategies regarding UAP.
- Exploring the intersection of UAP research with societal implications.
- Understanding the data, information and knowledge ecosystems surrounding UAP studies.
- Integrating discussions on UAP within the broader framework of the [NSF ASTRO ACCEL project](#).

The workshop will be an intimate, in-person gathering limited to approximately 25 participants. We are seeking intellectual representation across the following five themes:

- Information & Knowledge Construction
- Science Communication & Education
- Historical & Cultural Narratives
- Global/Political Affairs & Policy
- Scientific Research & Technology

We believe your [or your organization's] expertise and perspective could greatly enrich the discussions and outcomes of the event. If you are interested in attending and ultimately

contributing to a published report, please fill out the brief Expression of Interest form linked below. Additionally, if you require financial support for travel to the DC area, please indicate the approximate amount needed in the form.

Link:

Expression of Interest Deadline:

We look forward to receiving your expression of interest and hope to welcome you to this stimulating and timely workshop about a fascinating topic of widespread interest. Please feel free to forward this invitation to others with relevant expertise who may wish to attend as well.

Should you have any questions or require further information, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Warm regards,

[Your Name, Position, Organization]

[ASTRO ACCEL Logo]

Appendix C: Guidelines for Conduct

Workshop Focus: Please keep in mind that the workshop focus is around communication and education about UAPs. Specifically, discussion will focus on:

- Developing effective communication and education strategies regarding UAP,
- Exploring the intersection of UAP research with societal implications,
- Understanding the data, information and knowledge ecosystems surrounding UAP studies, and
- Integrating discussions on UAP within the broader framework of the NSF ASTRO ACCEL project.

It is important to note that we will not be focused on what UAP are or their origins, but rather how we can communicate and educate about UAP through the scientific lens. It is our hope that the work we do together can better normalize the conversation, data collection, data analysis, etc. about UAP within the research community and the general public. When we make something “taboo” or become dismissive of others’ observations/experiences, we create an opening for misinformation and misunderstanding to thrive. That is not good for anyone. Einstein once said, “No amount of experimentation can prove me right. A single experiment can prove me wrong.” This is why science and science communication/education must remain exploratory in nature. Just because we believe something to be true, it must not prevent us from giving consideration to an alternative conclusion supported by evidence.

A significant number of you are asking about who will attend the workshop. We fully expect there to be diverse opinions presented throughout the workshop, and we want to take time to make sure everyone who is attending will be comfortable sharing and will feel their thoughts and ideas are valued and respected. Our intent is to ensure we are creating a space where everyone can share what they are comfortable sharing. In an effort to create this space, we will be asking all participants to abide by these rules:

- Do not take pictures or video that include other attendees in them,
- Before sharing something you may have heard someone else say during the workshop, please secure their permission before repeating it and attributing it to them to others who are not in attendance at the workshop,
- While you may disagree, in some cases strongly, with the perspective of others, we ask that everyone work to maintain a professional and respectful attitude throughout.

Appendix D: Participant Consent Information Sheet

You are being asked to voluntarily participate in a research study. We are doing this study to accelerate research, education, and sharing of resources related to astronomy education, outreach, communications, and culture. If you choose to participate, you will be asked to attend and engage in a 2-day workshop. The workshop will be structured around group discussions and breakout sessions. All participants will sometimes meet as one working group and at other times will break into 3-5 working groups. Participants will be asked to elect one or more “reporters” for each group. This reporter will record individual contributions in a shared notes document set up for each group. When breakout group sessions end, a group spokesperson will report out to the entire group. This will be followed by exercises to prioritize outcomes and subsequent group activities.

This research is being funded by the National Science Foundation through the project *AccelNet-Implementation: The Global Network for Accelerating Synergies Through Research On Astronomy Culture, Communication, Education and Learning (ASTRO ACCEL)* (NSF award #2301922). You will not be paid to take part in this study.

We may publish the findings of the workshop so that the scholarly community will be aware of the opinions of the experts that attended and the decisions that were made. For administrative work such as this, human subjects informed consent is not needed, but since we intend to publish parts of this workshop informed consent is required. Participants will be invited to co-author a published report on workshop outcomes. Co-authorship can be declined.

We will securely store your information. Only members of the study team will have access to any identifiable information. We will store any paper files that contain identifiable information or your responses in locked filing cabinets. We will collect, transmit, store and access electronic files in computer systems with password, encryption, and other authentication protection. However, we cannot guarantee complete confidentiality.

If you have any questions, please contact Dr. Gretchen Stahlman (email: gstahlman@fsu.edu; telephone: 814-648-2317).

If you have any questions or concerns about your rights as a research participant, or questions or concerns regarding the study and would like to talk to someone other than the researcher(s), you are encouraged to contact the FSU Office for Human Subjects Protection (OHSP) at (850) 644-7900, by email at humansubjects@fsu.edu, or by mail at 2010 Levy Avenue, Research Foundation Building B, Suite 276, Tallahassee, FL 32306-2742.

Appendix E: Figures

Figure 1: Data-Information-Knowledge-Wisdom (DIKW) Pyramid
(Based on illustration of DIKW Pyramid - © User:Longlivetheux / Wikimedia Commons / CC-BY-SA-4.0)

Figure 2: “Phases of Information” Model
(Based on illustration of four fundamental states of matter with phase transitions - © User:ElfQrin / Wikimedia Commons / CC-BY-SA-4.0)

Figure 3: “Phases of Information” Breakout Groups

Appendix F: Breakout #2 Scenarios

K-12 Scenario: You are teaching a lesson on the solar system in your 8th grade Earth/Space Science class. One of your students begins sharing an experience they had where they observed something strange in the night sky that appeared to be moving rapidly in a zig-zag pattern, then disappeared suddenly. Other students in the class start to laugh.

- a) What would you do? What are the various ways of addressing the comment/situation?
- b) What are the opportunities here for learning related to scientific processes and astronomy/space science content?
- c) What existing resources might you point them to for additional information?
- d) What resources need to be developed to facilitate this learning?
- e) How might this learning align to the NGSS and other learning standards as well as standard 8th grade course curriculums?
- f) Other thoughts/points of interest

Public Scenario: You are leading a public tour of the solar system exhibit at the Smithsonian Air and Space Museum. A couple on the tour (look to be in their mid 40's) begins sharing an experience they had where they observed something strange in the night sky that appeared to be moving rapidly in a zig zag pattern, then disappeared suddenly. A few people in the tour begin to chuckle.

- a) What would you do? What are the various ways of addressing the comment/situation?
- b) What are the opportunities here for learning related to scientific processes and astronomy/space science content?
- c) What existing resources might you point them to for additional information?
- d) What resources need to be developed to facilitate best practices and learning?
- e) What thoughts do you have on an exhibit(s) that could be developed for science centers to help educate visitors about UAP?
- f) Other thoughts/points of interest

University Scenario: You are faculty at University of Wisconsin. It's Monday morning and today's lecture is on data collection and curation in astronomy. Over the weekend, Sunday evening, there was a UAP event that was visible over campus and across the region. Lots of images were posted on social media. While you did not experience the event personally, a number of your students were eyewitnesses to the event. At the beginning of the class, a couple of your students ask you about the event and describe their experience. One student speaks up and says, "You must have been on shrooms!" Other students break out in laughter.

- a) What would you do? What are the various ways of addressing the comment/situation?
- b) What are the opportunities here for learning related to scientific processes, astronomy/space science content, and data collection/curation?
- c) What existing resources might you point them to for additional information?
- d) What resources need to be developed to facilitate best practices and learning in this environment?
- e) Are there documents that could serve as a framework to facilitate learning for students at the university level?
- f) Other thoughts/points of interest